

Appendix -213- Framework for Assessing Weather-Induced Building Envelope Degradation and Its Impact on Energy Performance Under Current and Future Climate Conditions – NetZeroFuture2026 Conference

Table A1. Layer by layer thermal, optical, and mechanical properties measurement plan summary

Layer	Property / Damage Indicator	Related degradation mechanism	During aging	Measurement method/protocol
Whole Wall assembly	Air leakage	Interface opening, seal degradation, joint cracking, dimensional instability	Yes	ASTM E2357
Whole Wall assembly	Visual crack map / joint distress / discoloration	Thermal fatigue, shrinkage, debonding, surface aging	Yes	Photography
Whole Wall assembly	Surface temperatures (ext/int)	Thermal gradients, thermal shock	Yes	Thermocouples
Whole Wall assembly	Surface emissivity (ext/int)	Radiative aging, surface oxidation, finish degradation	No	ASTM E408
Whole Wall assembly	Solar reflectance (ext/int)	Radiative aging, surface oxidation, finish degradation	No	ASTM C1549
Brick veneer units	Visual damage	Thermal fatigue, surface cracking	Yes	Photography
Brick veneer units	Thermal conductivity	Moisture/pore change, microcracks affecting heat transfer	No	ASTM C518
Brick veneer units	Specific heat capacity	Material aging affecting heat storage	No	ASTM E1269
Mortar joints	Cracking / debonding	Thermal fatigue, shrinkage, bond degradation	Yes	Photography
Mortar joints	Thermal conductivity	Microcracking, porosity/moisture change	No	ASTM C518
Mortar joints	Specific heat capacity	Material aging, moisture-related changes	No	ASTM E1269
Cavity air space	Temperature	Heat buildup, transient thermal behavior	Yes	Thermocouples
Cavity air space	Relative humidity	Moisture accumulation, vapor trapping	Yes	RH sensors
House wrap surface	Temperature	Thermal stress at interface	Yes	Thermocouples
House wrap surface	Relative humidity	Interstitial condensation, slow drying	Yes	RH sensors
House wrap	Thermal properties	Material property drift	No	ASTM C518
Sheathing	Moisture content	Moisture accumulation, sorption damage	No	ASTM D4442
Sheathing	Thermal conductivity	Moisture-driven conductivity increase	No	ASTM C518
Sheathing	Specific heat capacity	Moisture/material aging effects	No	ASTM E1269
Sheathing	Swelling / warping	Structural degradation	No	Thickness measurement
Insulation	Thermal conductivity	Aging, moisture uptake, reduced R-value	No	ASTM C518
Insulation	Specific heat capacity	Thermal storage change	No	ASTM E1269
Metal ties / anchors	Corrosion / coating damage	Humidity-driven corrosion	No	Visual inspection
Metal ties / anchors	Looseness / displacement	Cyclic thermal movement, anchor slip	No	Manual inspection (displacement to ± 0.5 mm, feeler gauge)
Interior gypsum	Surface temperature	Heat transfer behavior	Yes	Thermocouples